

Economic life Of Kashkadarya during the period of Amir Temur and Temurids.

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Abstract: This article analyzes the economic life of the Kashkadarya oasis during the time of the Great Master Amir Temur and the Timurids, life style, market prices, taxes and their collection based on historical sources and ambassadors' diaries.

During the lifetime of Amir Temur, the economic situation of Movarounnahr people improved a lot. Claviho, the Spanish ambassador who was in Kesh (Shahrisabz) and Samarkand, says the following: "The next day, Thursday, August twenty-eight [1:1492-1495], at noon, we arrived at a large city called Kesh (Kesh). It was located on a flat land with streams and rivers crossing it on all sides. The city was surrounded by villages and gardens, in the surrounding plains there were many villages, farms, and hayfields, and it was clear that these places would be very beautiful in summer[2:135-138]. Grain on irrigated land. grapes, cotton, melons and tall fruit trees were growing. The city was surrounded by a wall and a deep moat, and there were drawbridges in front of the gates. When the Spanish ambassador was in Samarkand, Amir Temur was surprised that the capital was more prosperous. In the country of Movarounnahr, the thing that tamed him was the abundance of fruits, melons, watermelons, grain and rice in the orchards, and food was plentiful. "In these gardens," he recalls, "many melons and cotton are grown." The melons of this place are abundant and wonderful, until Mavlud (Christmas) they have so many melons and grapes that one can't help but wonder. Every day, so many [3:1-6] melons are brought on camels and sold and eaten that you will be surprised, man. In the villages, they are very clever, like figs, they dry them and save them from year to year. They keep them (melons) in this order: they cut them into slices, peel them, put them in the sun, after they dry [4:96-100], they collect them and put them in bags and use them throughout the year.

Amir Temur strove to create conditions for the prosperity and development of his estates in all aspects. At that time, livestock was over-extended, especially in the Kashkadarya oasis, special importance was attached to the breed of cattle. It is known that the butt of these sheep reached 20-40 kilos. When Claviho was in the country of Amir Temur, he did not ignore such sheep. In general, he said about Movarounnahr, "This place is prosperous for everything [5:121-123] - be it grain, wine, meat, fruit, and birds; the

sheep are very large and humpbacked, and some even have tails weighing twenty pounds, so heavy that a man can hardly lift them. Such sheep are extremely abundant and very cheap. When the lord (Sakhirqan) was in this place with his army, two fat sheep were valued at only one ducat. Other goods are also very cheap, even giving one and a half batmans of grain per mir, which is worth half a real. Bread is so cheap that it cannot be cheaper, and rice is unbelievably abundant [6:128-131]," said the ambassador of the Spanish ambassador.

In Movarounnahr at the end of the 14th century, abundance was not only in the food sector, but also in the clothing sector, which did not fail to surprise the foreign ambassador. Claviho, who knows well the life of the luxurious and luxurious royal palace in Europe [7:128-132], tries to compare the palaces of Amir Temur, and in general, everything he saw in this place, and he cannot help but admit that the buildings, fine gifts, and clothes of the country he came to as a guest are unique. He said: "The wealth of this country is not only in the abundance of its food, but also in silk fabrics, satin, bekasam, dukhoba, which are woven in many ways and are lined with wool and silk fabric, leather, gold-plated, and other colors [8: 73-76] can also be seen in clothes".

According to Ibn Arabshah's writings, Amir Temur had the right to rest and have fun in the gardens he created in Samarkand and its surroundings. It is known that Sahibgiron's time spent on a journey is ten times more important than his time in his capital. "If Temur went somewhere, Samarkand was free of his troops and assistants, and those bostons remained empty, the rich and the poor of the city's inhabitants would go to those bostons. For there was no better and more wonderful place of rest, more suitable and quieter for enjoyment than these gardens[9]. And the sweet, delicious fruits in the gardens were free for everyone. Because even a kilo of fruit was not sold, even if it was for a small price. By the way, V. V. Barthold also emphasized that Amir Temur's magnificent buildings were always open to the public and said that "Temur's palaces were not castles with locks for the public."

During the time of Amir Temur, laws were implemented without deviation from the point of view of protecting the interests of citizens. According to the testimony of the same Claviho, "Senor (Amir Temur) used to take with him the judges who served his Urdu and his household. When they come to a place, the inhabitants of that area[10:59-63] follow the word of the judges. These judges are assigned to solve various cases and are divided as follows: some of them deal with important cases and disputes, another manages the financial affairs of the lord (Temur), the third supervises the work of the governors of villages and towns subordinate to him, and another [11:26- 28] deals with ambassadors.

They put up three tents and see and decide the cases of those who come with complaints. Then they will tell Sen'or (Amir Temur) the result and issue a verdict on six or four appeals. Whenever they want to give a label to someone [12:86-90], the scribes in charge at this place write it down without a second thought and mark it in a notebook that is always at hand. The label is then presented to the sealer for review. The sealer wets the silver seal with ink and presses it on the inside of the label. Then someone else takes it, numbers it, and hands it to the head of the cabinet, who also puts his ink seal on it. In this way [13:386-391] after three or four sealers, they stamp the king's seal in the middle with the word "Truth". Rui González de Clavijo's extremely accurate presentation shows that complaints and problems in Amir Temur's office were not delayed, but were resolved quickly. The tyranny of the royal courts was cut off, a strict control procedure, which did not allow for arbitrariness in the granting of privileges, and the method of personal responsibility was implemented. Amir Temur took all measures to protect the interests of the people, to protect them from bandits and thieves.

Amir Temur, who strictly adheres to Sharia rules, regulates the taxes collected from the people. In particular, it cancels the stamp tax imposed on artisans and merchants during the Mongol era, and juzya (capitation tax levied on non-religious people). The cancellation of the stamp tax [14:292-296] will stimulate the rapid development of handicrafts and trade in the country. Amir Temur's capital, Samarkand, and then Shahrisabz, were densely populated, and most of them were craftsmen. Some of the craftsmen were brought from other countries. As in Samarkand, Shahrisabz and Karshi madrasahs were well provided during the time of Amir Temur. This undoubtedly indicates that economic life was good in these cities.

References:

1. Hasanov, A. (2020). Kesh-Shakhrisabz oasis in the middle ages. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(5), 1492-1495.
2. Khudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Guzar's ethymology in Historical Sources. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 2(3), 135-138.
3. Muminovich, H. A. (2022). TERRITORIAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF THE CITIES OF THE TERMIZ OASIS IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 6, 1-6.
4. Khasanov, A. M. (2021). Historical and Geographical Regions of Chaghaniyan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(4), 96-100

5. Karimov, B. (2021). Historical Geography of Yakkabog District. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(4), 121-123.
6. Xudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Handicraft and Trade in Guzar District. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(8), 128-131.
7. Eshov, B. J., & Hasanov, A. M. (2016). CERTAIN REASONINGS ABOUT ANCIENT LOCAL POPULATION AND THE NOMADIC OF CENTRAL ASIA. *Education Transformation Issues*, (1), 128-132.
8. Muminov, U. (2021). Historical Gates of Karshi. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(6), 73-76.
9. Xudoyqulovich, B. K. D. E. A. (2021). HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHICAL CLASSIFICATION AND ECONOMIC, SOCIO-POLITICAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE GUZAR DEPARTMENT IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIX CENTURY CONDITION. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol*, 27(5).
10. Bahrom, K. (2022). SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE AND ADMINISTRATIVE TERRITORY OF SHAKHRISABZ PRINCIPALITY IN THE 19TH CENTURY. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(09), 59-63.
11. Matluba, R. (2022). THE ROLE OF THE HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF THE KASHKADARYA OASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 6, 26-28.
12. Bahrom, K. (2022). Political-Administrative Territory of The City of Karshi in The Second Half of The 19th Century-The Beginning of The 20th Century. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 1(2), 86-90.
13. Мўминов, У. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE CITY OF KARSHI IN FOREIGN TRADE. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 2(14), 386-391.
14. Khudoykulovich, E. A. (2023). ISSUES OF THE HISTORICAL-GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF GUZAR DISTRICT. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 2(14), 292-296.

